

Quantitative Treatment of The Variation of The Mean Activity Coefficient of The Ions in Solutions of Strong Electrolytes with Dilution

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It has been shown that starting with Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium for non-ideal solutions a modified expression for χ (Kappa) of the Debye-Huckel theory of strong electrolytes can be deduced. This modified expression for χ is exactly the same as has been deduced in a previous paper by applying Boltzmann formula to the distribution of the ions in the ion-atmosphere of the central positively charged ion, taking into consideration the mean activity coefficient of the ions of the electrolyte in solution.

The equation for the variation of the mean activity coefficient of the ions with the concentration of the electrolyte in solution deduced by using this modified χ has been subjected to test on a few 1:1 electrolytes using the data available in literature and has been found satisfactory within the range of concentration investigated.

From the 'effective ionic diameter', A , contained in the expression for the modified χ , hydration values of the ions of the electrolytes used have been calculated. The order of hydration of the cations thus calculated agrees with that recorded by other authors. The "effective ionic diameter" of CsCl has been found to be $0.74\text{\AA}$ larger than the sum of the ionic radii of the Cs^+ and Cl^- ions.

In a previous publication¹, attempts of Eigen and Wicke² and Dutta and Bagchi³ to replace the Boltzmann formula for the distribution of ions in the ion-atmosphere of the central ion by new ones developed by them were mentioned. Falkenhagen and Kelbg⁴ have also proposed another distribution formula. Further work on the refinement and application of the different distribution formulae is to be found in the publication of these⁵⁻⁸ and other authors⁹⁻¹¹. A brief assessment of these formulae has been made by Redlich¹². Sen Gupta^{10,11} has used the distribution formulae of Dutta and Bagchi and Bagchi⁶ for the calculation of the mean activity coefficient, f of a few 1:1 and 2:1 electrolytes under a variety of conditions in the concentration range of 0.1 M and above and has shown that by proper adjustment of suitable parameters, the theoretical $\log f$ versus molarity curves can be made to run close to the experimental curves. Bagchi¹³ has used his distribution formula assuming linear approximation of the ion-atmosphere potential for the calculation of equilibrium thermodynamic properties of some molten alkali halides. The results obtained by him appear to be promising.

It may, however, be pointed out that all the investigators who have applied these distribution formulae and also the Boltzmann formula to solutions of electrolytes have taken such solutions as ideal to start with.

In this connection it may be mentioned that in Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium[†] for non-ideal solutions, the mean activity coefficient of the ions has been taken into account in dealing with the distribution of ions between the ion-atmosphere and the bulk of the solution where the potential due to the ion-atmosphere is zero. Under equilibrium conditions for solutions containing a 1:1 electrolyte the equations may be written as follows:

$$(n_+)(f)(n_-)(f) = (nf_0)^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{and } (n_-)(f)/(nf_0) = (nf_0)/(n_+)(f) = K, \text{ a constant} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{(n_-)f}{nf_0} = \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{nf_0}{(n_+)f} \\ = \frac{kT}{e} \ln K = -\psi \quad \dots (2a)$$

In equation (1), $(n_+)(f)(n_-)(f)$ represents the products of the activities of the positive and negative ions of the electrolyte in the ion-atmosphere having potential ψ and $(nf_0)^2$ the product of the activities of the oppositely charged ions in the

[†] Since it is now generally accepted that the ion-atmosphere surrounding say a central positive ion of a strong electrolyte in solution possesses all the characteristics of the ion-atmosphere surrounding a colloidal or protein ion, so there can be no objection to extending the application of Donnan's theory to such ion-atmospheres of simple ions. It may also be noted that when the central positive ion undergoes brownian movement it carries its ion-atmosphere with it.

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bulk of the solution where $\psi=0$ and f and f_0 represent the *mean molar activity* coefficient of the ions in the ion-atmosphere and in the bulk of the solution respectively.

It follows from equation (2a) that the density of electric charge, $\rho = en(f_0/f)[\exp(-e\psi/kT) - \exp(e\psi/kT)]$... (3)

Assuming linear approximation of ion-atmosphere potential, equation (3) may be written as follows :

$$\rho = -\left[\frac{2ne^2}{kT} \psi(f_0/f)\right] \quad \dots (3a)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \nabla^2 \psi = \frac{-4\pi\rho}{D} = \left[\frac{8\pi e^2 n}{DkT}\right] (f_0/f)\psi \quad \dots (4)$$

$$= \chi^2 \psi \quad \dots (4a)$$

where
$$\chi = \left[\frac{8\pi e^2 n}{DkT}\right]^{1/2} (f_0/f)^{1/2}$$

It is to be noted that χ in equation (4a) differs from the Debye-Huckel χ (Kappa) by the factor (f_0/f) .

It may be mentioned that exactly the same expression for χ as in equation (4a) has also been deduced by the author¹ in a previous paper by applying Boltzmann formula to the distribution of ions in the ion-atmosphere of the central positively charged ion taking into consideration the mean activity coefficient of the ions of the electrolyte in solution. Therefore, the expression for modified χ as in equation (4a) may be applied with confidence to solutions of strong electrolytes where necessary, as it can be derived in different ways.

It has been shown in the previous paper¹ that $(f_0/f)^{1/2}$ in χ in equation (4a) can be replaced by $(n^1/n)^{1/2}$ by applying Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium and $(2n)^{1/2}$ can be replaced by $(2n)^{1/2}/(2\pi ax)^{1/2}$ and the expression for the modified χ can be written as follows :

$$\chi = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTa}\right] (2n)^{1/2} \left[\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (5)$$

where a represents the "effective ionic parameter" and x , a dimensionless variable.

In equation (5) both n^1/n and x decrease as the electrolyte concentration n increases. Therefore, it has been assumed that over a certain range of concentration of the electrolyte the ratio $\left[\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right]$ may remain constant* and over that range of concentration the following expression should hold good.

$$\chi = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTA}\right]^{1/2} (2n)^{1/2} \quad \dots (5a)$$

where $A = a/\theta$ and $\theta = \left[\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right]$, a constant.

It has also been shown in the previous paper¹ that, using the aforesaid expression for χ , the variation of the mean molar activity coefficient f with the

* In a previous publication¹ reasons have been put forward for treating $\left[\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right]$ as close to unity.

concentration c of the electrolyte may be represented by the following equations :

$$-\log f = B/(A)^{1/2} [C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}] \quad \dots (6)$$

$$= 0.60/(A)^{1/2} [C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}] \text{ at } 0^\circ \quad \dots (6a)$$

$$= 0.624/(A)^{1/2} [C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}] \text{ at } 25^\circ \quad \dots (6b)$$

where B , C_0 and A are constants and C the concentration of the electrolyte in moles per liter. C_0 represents the concentration at which $\log f=0$ and A has been termed "effective ionic diameter".

In this paper equations (6a) and (6b) have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on a few 1 : 1 electrolytes with a view to ascertain the concentration range in which it holds good and correlate A with the extent of hydration, H , of the ions of the electrolytes used. The following expression has been used connecting H with A .

$$H = [A - (\gamma_+ + \gamma_-)] \quad \dots (7)$$

where γ_+ and γ_- represent the crystallographic radii of the cation and the anion of the electrolyte used. It is to be noted that A represents the sum of the crystallographic radii of the cation and the anion of the electrolyte when $H=0$.

Processing of data :

In Table 1 are recorded the data on the mean molar activity coefficient f corresponding to different concentrations C (in moles per liter) collected from Table 1, Appendix 8.7 of Robinson and Stokes^{1,4} "Electrolyte Solution". Under the head miscellaneous, in column 1 are mentioned the electrolyte, the equation used and the values of the constants in the equation. Obsd. f and calcd. f represent the observed and calculated values of f . In this paper no distinction has been made between molal and molar concentration upto 0.1M.

In Table 2 are recorded the data collected from Table 2, chapter 8 contributed by Frank and Thompson^{1,5} to "the Structure of Electrolytic solutions". In column 1 of Table 2 are mentioned the electrolytes used, b in column 2 is to be identified with $0.624/(A)^{1/2}$ in equation (6b). A and H have the same significance as explained already. It appears that a printing error had occurred in the recorded value of b of CsCl in Table 2 of the aforesaid authors^{1,5}. The value of 0.330 recorded therein does not agree with the observed value of activity coefficient f of CsCl at 0.1M. It should be read as 0.303 instead of 0.330.

Table 3 is similar to Table 2, but the values of A have been found from $(A)^{1/2}$ recorded in Table 1 of this paper and correspond to the temperature of the freezing point of the electrolyte solutions used.

The constants A and C_0 in the equations (6a) and (6b) have been calculated from the experimental data using two known values of $-\log f$ corresponding to two given values of C .

Discussion

Variation of mean activity coefficient with concentration : It will be noticed from the data recorded

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF *f* WITH *C* FROM FREEZING POINT MEASUREMENT

Miscellaneous	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
KNO₃	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.33$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.966	0.953	0.927	0.899	0.862	0.794	0.726
(A) ^{1/2} =1.82, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.064	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.972	0.955	0.922	0.892	0.854	0.794	0.738
NaNO₃	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.29$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.954	0.931	0.906	0.874	0.818	0.765
(A) ^{1/2} =2.07, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.061	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.973	0.957	0.929	0.902	0.869	0.815	0.764
LiNO₃	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.227$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.955	0.932	0.910	0.882	0.839	0.804
(A) ^{1/2} =2.64, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.085	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.954	0.931	0.910	0.883	0.841	0.799
KCl	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.265$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.954	0.930	0.905	0.874	0.821	0.773
(A) ^{1/2} =2.26, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.046	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.963	0.953	0.927	0.902	0.872	0.822	0.775
NaCl	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.245$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.955	0.931	0.909	0.880	0.831	0.787
(A) ^{1/2} =2.45, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.011	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.953	0.929	0.906	0.878	0.830	0.788
LiCl	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.218$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.964	0.950	0.924	0.899	0.870	0.826	0.791
(A) ^{1/2} =2.42, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.04	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.966	0.952	0.928	0.905	0.877	0.829	0.785
KBr	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.248$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.954	0.931	0.906	0.876	0.824	0.778
(A) ^{1/2} =2.42, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.042	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.966	0.953	0.929	0.906	0.877	0.830	0.785
NaBr	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.221$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.968	0.957	0.937	0.917	0.891	0.847	0.808
(A) ^{1/2} =2.71, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.034	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.954	0.935	0.912	0.886	0.844	0.804
LiBr	C	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6a) $B/(A)^{1/2}=0.214$	Obsd. <i>f</i>	0.967	0.955	0.934	0.918	0.886	0.847	0.817
(A) ^{1/2} =2.80, (Co) ^{1/2} =0.033	Calcd. <i>f</i>	0.968	0.955	0.934	0.914	0.889	0.847	0.809

TABLE 2—VALUES OF *H* (HYDRATION) OF IONS AT 25°

Electrolyte used	<i>b</i>	<i>A</i> Angstrom	<i>H</i> Angstrom	Electrolyte used	<i>b</i>	<i>A</i> Angstrom	<i>H</i> Angstrom
CsCl	0.303	4.24	0.74	KBr	0.258	5.86	2.58
RbCl	0.278	5.06	1.77	KI	0.228	7.51	4.02
KCl	0.269	5.38	2.24				

TABLE 3—VALUES OF *H* (HYDRATION) OF IONS AT THE FREEZING POINT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

Electrolyte used	<i>A</i> Angstrom	<i>H</i> Angstrom	Electrolyte used	<i>A</i> Angstrom	<i>H</i> Angstrom
KNO ₃	3.31	0.27	LiCl	5.86	3.45
NaNO ₃	4.23	1.52	KBr	5.43	2.15
LiNO ₃	4.56	2.23	NaBr	7.34	4.44
KCl	5.11	1.97	LiBr	7.84	5.29
NaCl	6.0	3.24			

in Table 1 that in the concentration range 0.001*M* to 0.1*M* the values of *f* calculated by using equation (6a) agree with those observed for all the electrolytes used, except KNO₃ at 0.1*M*, within one per cent. In the case of KNO₃, at 0.1*M* the value of calculated *f* differs from that observed by about 1.5 per cent. It may, therefore, be concluded that the assumption that $\left[\frac{n^2/n}{x}\right]$ remains constant is valid for the aforesaid electrolytes within the concentration range investigated.

The values of *H* (hydration) of the electrolytes investigated: The values of *H* (in Angström) have been calculated by using equation (7). The values of *b* recorded in Table 2 have been collected from Frank and Thompson's article¹⁵ in "The Structure of Electrolytic Solutions". These authors, from the consideration of a "diffuse lattice Model", have guessed that variation of log *f* with *C* may be represented by the following equation:

$$\log f = a - bC^{1/2} + SC^{4/3} \quad \dots (a)$$

They actually applied the equation $\log f = a - bC^{1/2}$ to a few alkali metal salt solutions at 25° and recorded the values of *a* and *b* in Table 2 of their article¹⁵. It is to be noted that *b* in their equation is to be identified with $0.624/(A)^{1/2}$ in the equation (6b) of the present author.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 2 of this paper that the value of *H* for CsCl is small and *A* "the effective ionic diameter" differs from the sum of the crystallographic radii of the

Cs^+ and Cl^- ions by $0.74 \text{ \AA}$ only. A comparison of the values of H of KCl , KBr and KI indicates that the hydration of the cation K^+ is influenced by the anion with which it is combined. An anion of large radius such as the I^- ion, cannot penetrate the hydration sheath of the cation and approach so close to it as an anion of relatively small size such as Cl^- ion can do. This point has been discussed in some detail by Robinson and Stokes¹⁶.

The data recorded in Table 3 show that the value of H for KNO_3 is quite small. In this case $1.71 \text{ \AA}$, the radius of ionic nitrogen has been used for calculation, since the ionic radius of NO_3^- is not known. It is assumed that the radius of NO_3^- cannot be less than the radius of ionic nitrogen. The order of hydration of the nitrates are $\text{Li} > \text{Na} > \text{K}$.

A comparison of the values of H for the alkali chlorides recorded in the Tables 2 and 3 shows that the order of hydration is $\text{Li} > \text{Na} > \text{K} > \text{Rb}$ which is the reverse of the order of their ionic radii. The same order for the alkali halides has also been observed by other authors^{16,17}.

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